

Moment-based nonlinear energy-maximising optimal control of wave energy systems to secure a renewable future

Work Package WP2

Experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control

Deliverable D2.2

Report on WP2

Funding Instrument: Marie-Sklodowska Curie Actions - Individual Fellowships (MSCA-IF)
Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2020
Project Start: 1 June 2021
Project Duration: 24 months

Beneficiary in Charge: Politecnico di Torino
Researcher: Nicolás Faedo

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	DESTINY
Project Number:	Grant Agreement N°101024372
Deliverable Number:	D2.2
Deliverable Full Title:	Report on WP2
Deliverable Short Title:	R-WP1
Document Identifier:	DESTINY-D22-RWP-final
Beneficiary in Charge:	Politecnico di Torino
Report Version:	v1.0
Contractual Date:	–
Report Submission Date:	1/06/2022
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	Nicolás Faedo
Co-author(s):	
Keywords:	
Status:	_ draft, x final, _ submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
01/06/2022	v1.0	Nicolás Faedo	First version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Project overview	5
2. Objectives and main contributions of WP2.....	7
2.1 Specific objectives.....	7
2.2 Roadmap WP2.....	7
2.3 Contributions	8
3. List of publications associated to WP2.....	9
References	11

Executive Summary

This document constitutes Deliverable 2.2 of the H2020-MSCA-IF-2020 **Destiny's** project (Grant Agreement No 101024372). *Destiny is a project dedicated to advance the state-of-the-art of WEC control technology by providing a novel and reliable nonlinear optimal control framework, maximising energy absorption for a wide range of ocean conditions for single and multiple devices, exhibiting real-time capabilities and globally optimal performance. The final aim is to provide all stakeholders in the wave energy field with a fundamental tool to facilitate reaching economic viability of wave energy technology.*

In particular, this document constitutes a report of the work done throughout work package 2 (WP2), on the **experimental assessment and validation** of moment-based optimal control for wave energy systems. To achieve such an objective, this WP includes: 1) Experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control within a state-of-the-art hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) facility available at the partner institution Maynooth University, and 2) experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control for a prototype wave energy conversion system within the wave tank facilities available at Aalborg University.

1 Project overview

Ocean waves have an enormous potential, capable of fulfilling 20% of the global energy demand, making a decisive contribution towards a low-carbon energy society, addressing number 7 (affordable and clean energy), 11 (sustainable cities and communities), and 13 (climate action) of the United Nation Development Goals. As a matter of fact, to achieve the 2030 Climate & Energy Framework and the Roadmap 2050 targets, the European Union (EU) highly encourages development of the ocean renewable energy field, which can potentially mitigate EU dependence on fossil fuels, directly contributing to Europe's decarbonisation goals by 2030 and 2050. Despite being a vast resource, wave energy converters (WECs) have not yet been successfully commercialised. The lack of proliferation of wave energy can be attributed to its current levelised cost of energy (LCoE), which is substantially higher than other renewable energy sources (see *e.g.* (Ringwood, Bacelli, & Fusco, 2014)).

Control system technology can impact WEC design and operation, by maximising energy extraction from waves, and optimising energy conversion in the power take-off (PTO) actuator system. In particular, the central problem in WEC control is to find a technically feasible way to 'act' on the device (via the PTO) so that energy absorption from waves is maximised while minimising the risk of component damage (Faedo, 2020; Faedo, Olaya, & Ringwood, 2017). Such a control process can be written in terms of an *optimal control problem*, where the objective is to design a suitable control algorithm capable of enhancing the performance of WECs, as schematically illustrated in Figure 1. It is already clear that control technology can enhance WECs performance in a wide range of ocean conditions, substantially reducing the LCoE. In other words, the design of appropriate control technology, together with an economy of scale facilitated through array configurations, constitute key stepping-stones towards successful commercialisation of WEC technology.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of optimal WEC control.

Using knowledge from both the external forces (such as the force exerted by waves), the measured motion of the device, and a suitable control-oriented dynamical model, an optimally designed control algorithm can substantially increase the energy absorbed from the wave resource. A particularly efficient control framework for wave energy systems is based upon the notion of moments (Faedo, Scarciotti, Astolfi, & Ringwood, 2021a, 2021b; Faedo, 2020). *Moments* are mathematical objects which relate to the steady-state response of the WEC device, being able to transcribe the energy-maximising infinite-dimensional optimal control problem for wave energy extraction systems, to a computationally tractable optimisation program. To achieve this, moment-based theory combines a number of fundamental concepts arising in system dynamics and control, including centre manifold theory, approximation theory, and the concept of invariance (see *e.g.* (Isidori, 2013)), as schematically detailed in Figure 2.

Though already efficient and highly competitive, moment-based control for WECs still requires of development to thrive in real-world scenarios. **Destiny** will greatly advance the state-of-the-

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of moment-based theory and WEC control.

art of this family of controllers, by means of four (4) main research objectives (ROs), each of these associated with a specific work package (WP), as follows (see also Figure 3):

- **RO1–WP1 (Extension class of nonlinearities):** The first core research objective of Destiny is to extend the nonlinear moment-based WEC control framework by including relevant IDNs in the corresponding energy-maximising OCP. This will systematically guarantee optimal performance for a large class of devices, featuring an accurate nonlinear description of the WEC dynamics, directly advancing the state-of-the-art of WEC control.
- **RO2–WP2 (Controller validation):** The second core objective of Destiny is to perform a full experimental validation of the extended moment-based nonlinear control framework, allowing its reliable utilisation in real-world scenarios.
- **RO3–WP3 (Extension to WEC arrays):** The third core research objective of Destiny is to incorporate multiple devices to the newly extended (via WP1) and fully validated (via WP2) nonlinear moment-based framework, hence being able to include arrays in the energy-maximising control design procedure, advancing the state-of-the-art of WEC control, following and supporting the pathway towards effective commercialisation of WEC technology.
- **RO4–WP4 (Software release):** The final core research objective of Destiny is to release an open-source software, ‘Control for all’ (CONTRALL), to design and test the novel moment-based controller for a given (user-selected) device. CONTRALL will be readily available, coded in a user-friendly environment, directly benefiting WEC developers and stakeholders in the process of design and commercialisation of both existing, and novel devices.

As such, the control framework resulting of **Destiny** will feature an accurate description of the physics associated with the wave energy extraction process, optimally maximising energy absorption for single devices and array configurations, and exhibiting real-time capabilities. This will provide all stakeholders in the ocean engineering and wave energy fields with a fundamental and easily accessible tool to facilitate reaching economic viability of WEC technology.

Figure 3: Destiny WPs and their synergy and interconnection.

2 Objectives and main contributions of WP2

2.1 Specific objectives

The objectives of this specific work package comprise two fundamental items:

1. Experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control within a hardware-in-the-loop facility.
2. Experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control within a wave tank, in realistic (operative) sea-state conditions.

Given the ultimate objective of **Destiny**, *i.e.* delivering a general framework for optimal control of wave energy systems, Item 1) above is required as a first step towards experimental assessment and validation of the proposed control technique, particularly for WEC systems subject to non-ideal PTO effects. Item 2) effectively aims at providing experimental assessment and validation of moment-based WEC control within realistic sea-state conditions. To fulfill such an objective, the controller is tested in a prototype WEC system, within state-of-the-art experimental wave tank facilities.

A number of contributions have been originated while achieving 1) and 2), including a set of complementary tools and experimental results. A full list of the research publications associated with the contributions of WP2 can be found here in Section 3. Note that final author versions for every published publication can be openly downloaded from the [POLITO IRIS repository](#).

2.2 Roadmap WP2

Figure 4 illustrates the main technical components of WP2, along with the corresponding list of associated contributions in form of peer-reviewed research publications (see Section 3). Such fundamental parts of WP2 are listed in the following:

- *Moment-based control experimental assessment & validation hardware-in-the-loop* - Publications (1) and (2).
- *Moment-based control experimental assessment & validation wave tank* - Publication (3).

Each of these fundamental components, and their associated contributions, are described in

detail within Section 4, along with wave tank experimental assessment and validation of the set of optimality conditions derived in WP1 of Destiny's action (Publications (4) and (5)).

WEC moment-based control experimental assessment and validation

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of WP2 main contributions.

2.3 Contributions

Experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control

To date, practical results regarding moment-based control for WEC systems are exclusively provided in numerical simulation environments, *i.e.* there is a lack of experimental assessment and validation of such a control framework. This is, clearly, fundamental to demonstrating the concrete feasibility of the technique in realistic scenarios, hence providing tangible proof of reliability for any candidate WEC technology stakeholder. Motivated by the potential exhibited by this WEC optimal control strategy, and the intrinsic requirement of ‘real-world’ testing for its reliable utilisation, within this WP, a comprehensive experimental assessment and validation of energy-maximising moment-based control for the WEC application is provided.

First, an experimental assessment and validation of moment-based control within a hardware-in-the-loop system, located within the facilities of the partner institution (Centre for Ocean Energy Research, Maynooth University, Ireland), is provided. In particular, the controller is tested within a variety of sea-state conditions, for a rotational flap-type WEC system. Non-ideal PTO effects are considered within the control calculation, aiming to validate the capabilities exhibited by the controller in such scenario. The technical details regarding the specific control loop configuration tested can be found in Publication (1), while experimental results and assessment are published within Publication (2).

Secondly, and aiming to provide a full assessment and validation of moment-based control within realistic sea-state operating conditions, a prototype of the Wavestar WEC system, available within the tank-testing facilities of the Department of the Built Environment, Aalborg University, Denmark, is considered. Note that this same system and setup has been previously chosen as an experimental benchmark case for WEC control testing, specifically within the first edition of the so-called Wave Energy Control Competition (WEC³OMP), as described in (Ringwood et al., 2019), demonstrating its suitability and representativeness for testing energy-maximising control algorithms. This particular task of WP2 presents an integrated account of moment-based control design, synthesis, and real-time implementation procedures, hence filling the gap between the theoretical aspects associated with such a control framework, and the corresponding practical application. This includes experimental system identification of the

WEC system (leading to a suitable model for control and estimation purposes); design, synthesis, and validation of the unknown-input estimator and forecasting strategies adopted, required to provide instantaneous and future estimates of the wave resource for control calculations, respectively; and tuning, implementation, and validation of the integrated moment-based control architecture. Specific details of such experimental assessment and validation can be found in Publication (3).

On the experimental assessment and validation of the optimality conditions derived in WP1

Within WP1 of Destiny's action (see (Faedo, 2022)), a comprehensive derivation and discussion on the idealised theoretical optimal control conditions for maximum energy absorption in underactuated multi degree-of-freedom (DoF) WEC systems is derived. In particular, the optimality principle for single-DoF devices is extended to underactuated multi-DoF systems, and a set of optimality conditions is explicitly proposed. In addition, the impact and use of this set of (generic) optimal conditions for control design and synthesis is explicitly discussed.

Within this WP, an experimental validation of such optimality conditions for multi-DoF WECs is also proposed, considering a scaled prototype of a multi-DoF inertial wave energy conversion system. The experimental campaign has been conducted within the tank facilities available at Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, subject to a variety of wave conditions. Two different control structures have been adopted to realise the derived optimality conditions, namely coupled proportional, and coupled proportional-integral, controllers, fully tuned based upon interpolation of a particular non-parametric empirical transfer function, which defines the optimal frequency-domain input-output response for energy-maximising behaviour. Technical details of such experimental assessment and validation can be found in Publication (4).

Finally, and also based upon the derived optimality conditions within WP1, an extension of the control technique (García-Violini, Peña-Sanchez, Faedo, & Ringwood, 2020) has been tested and presented as part of this WP. Technical details can be found within Publication (5).

3 List of publications associated to WP2

This section contains a list of peer-reviewed publications (in chronological order), which constitute outcomes/results associated with WP2. The following shorthand notation is used to denote the status of the publication: (P) published, (A) accepted, (UR) under review.

Final author versions for every published (P) publication can be openly downloaded from the [POLITO IRIS repository](#).

N°	Status	Publication
(1)	(A)	F. Mosquera, N. Faedo, C. Evangelista, P. Puleston, J. V. Ringwood, "Energy-maximising tracking control for a nonlinear heaving point absorber system via second order sliding modes", 14th IFAC Conference on Control Applications in Marine Systems, Robotics and Vehicles, Lyngby, 2022.
(2)	(UR)	N. Faedo, F. Mosquera, C. Evangelista, J. V. Ringwood, P. Puleston, "Preliminary experimental assessment of second-order sliding mode control for wave energy conversion systems", 2022 Australian and New Zealand Control Conference, Gold Coast, 2022.

N°	Status	Publication
(3)	(UR)	N. Faedo, Y. Pena-Sanchez, D. García-Violini, F. Ferri, G. Mattiazzo, J. V. Ringwood, “Experimental assessment and validation of energy-maximising moment-based optimal control for a prototype wave energy converter”, <i>Control Engineering Practice</i> , 2022.
(4)	(A)	N. Faedo, E. Pasta, F. Carapellese, V. Orlando, D. Pizzirusso, D. Basile, S. A. Sirigu, “Experimental energy-maximising control tuning via impedance-matching for a multi-degree-of-freedom wave energy converter”, 14th IFAC Conference on Control Applications in Marine Systems, Robotics and Vehicles, Lyngby, 2022.
(5)	(UR)	D. Garcia-Violini, Y. Pena-Sanchez, N. Faedo, F. Ferri, J. V. Ringwood, “A broadband time-varying energy maximising control for wave energy systems (LiTe-Con+): Framework and experimental validation”, <i>IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy</i> , 2022.

References

- Faedo, N. (2020). *Optimal control and model reduction for wave energy systems: A moment-based approach* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Department of Electronic Engineering, Maynooth University.
- Faedo, N. (2022). *Destiny - deliverable 1.2: Extension class of nonlinearities* (Tech. Rep. No. V2.0). Turin, Italy: Politecnico di Torino. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797741>
- Faedo, N., Olaya, S., & Ringwood, J. V. (2017). Optimal control, mpc and mpc-like algorithms for wave energy systems: An overview. *IFAC Journal of Systems and Control*, 1, 37–56.
- Faedo, N., Scarciotti, G., Astolfi, A., & Ringwood, J. V. (2021a). Nonlinear energy-maximizing optimal control of wave energy systems: A moment-based approach. *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, 29(6), 2533–2547.
- Faedo, N., Scarciotti, G., Astolfi, A., & Ringwood, J. V. (2021b). On the approximation of moments for nonlinear systems. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 66(11), 5538–5545.
- García-Violini, D., Peña-Sánchez, Y., Faedo, N., & Ringwood, J. V. (2020). An energy-maximising linear time invariant controller (lite-con) for wave energy devices. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 11(4), 2713–2721.
- Isidori, A. (2013). *Nonlinear control systems*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Ringwood, J., Bacelli, G., & Fusco, F. (2014). Energy-maximizing control of wave-energy converters: The development of control system technology to optimize their operation. *IEEE Control Systems*, 34(5), 30–55.
- Ringwood, J., Ferri, F., Tom, N., Ruehl, K., Faedo, N., Bacelli, G., ... Coe, R. G. (2019). The wave energy converter control competition: Overview. In *International conference on offshore mechanics and arctic engineering* (Vol. 58899, p. V010T09A035).

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the DESTINY project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

The results presented in this document reflect only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.